

Black Hole with Primary Scalar Hair Surrounded by a Cloud of Strings: Thermodynamic and Radiative Properties

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We investigate the thermodynamic, optical, and radiative properties of a black hole with primary scalar hair surrounded by a cloud of strings. The spacetime is characterized by the mass parameter M , the string-cloud parameter α , the scalar-hair combination $\beta = \eta q^4$, and the length scale λ associated with the scalarized core. The model combines two independent sources of strong-field deviations from the Schwarzschild geometry: primary scalar hair, which modifies the short-distance structure of the metric, and a string cloud, which produces a conical-deficit-like deformation of the asymptotic geometry. We analyze the horizon structure, Hawking temperature, heat capacity, Gibbs free energy, sparsity of Hawking radiation, photon sphere, shadow radius, and spectral energy emission rate. The scalar hair and the string cloud affect the near-horizon geometry in complementary ways: increasing α enlarges the horizon and the shadow, whereas increasing positive β tends to reduce the relevant characteristic radii in the parameter range considered. The heat capacity and Gibbs free energy reveal changes in local and global thermodynamic behavior. The sparsity parameter remains much larger than unity in the physical domain, confirming the dilute character of Hawking radiation. Finally, the emission spectrum displays the expected Hawking-like profile, with a peak whose position and amplitude are controlled by the scalar-hair and string-cloud parameters.

Keywords: Modified gravity theories; black hole; thermodynamics; shadow; sparsity of Hawking flux; energy emission rate

I. INTRODUCTION

The thermodynamics of black holes continues to be one of the most important and actively studied subjects in theoretical physics. Black holes exhibit thermodynamic behavior analogous to that of ordinary thermodynamic systems, obeying laws that closely resemble the four laws of thermodynamics [1–5]. Furthermore, they possess entropy [6, 7] and are believed to have an underlying microscopic structure [8–10], pointing toward a profound connection between gravitation, quantum mechanics, and statistical physics.

Hawking radiation renders black holes thermodynamically unstable within the semiclassical framework, as the emission of particles leads to a continuous loss of mass and an associated increase in temperature [11]. Consequently, black holes evolve through a runaway evaporation process in which smaller black holes become progressively hotter. A central aspect of black-hole thermodynamics is therefore their thermal stability. Stability can be assessed by examining the response of the system to small perturbations in thermodynamic variables, since stable configurations should return to equilibrium after such fluctuations. In the study of black-hole phase structure, particularly near critical points, several complementary

diagnostic tools are available [12]. Among these, the heat capacity plays a key role, as it directly characterizes thermal response and stability. In general, a positive heat capacity indicates local thermodynamic stability, while a negative value signals instability [13, 14]. Phase transitions in black-hole systems are often associated with divergences or sign changes in the heat capacity. Such divergences typically indicate second-order (continuous) phase transitions, where thermodynamic quantities vary smoothly but response functions become singular. For example, the Schwarzschild black hole exhibits a negative heat capacity, reflecting its intrinsic thermodynamic instability under Hawking radiation [15, 16]. In contrast, the divergence of heat capacity near critical points signals transitions between distinct thermodynamic phases, analogous to critical phenomena in ordinary thermodynamic systems such as fluids. These features highlight the deep parallels between black-hole physics and conventional statistical mechanics.

In classical General Relativity, the exterior geometry of an isolated, stationary black hole is highly constrained by the no-hair theorems, with the Schwarzschild solution representing the simplest asymptotically flat vacuum configuration. Nevertheless, this classical description is expected to break down in the strong-curvature regime, where the presence of singularities and the loss of predictability suggest the need for quantum-gravity effects or effective modifications of General Relativity. In this context, regular or regularized black-hole geometries arising in modified-gravity theories and scalar-field extensions provide useful theoretical laboratories for exploring departures from the Schwarzschild spacetime.

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Among such extensions, black holes endowed with *primary scalar hair* are of particular interest [17]. Unlike secondary hair, whose magnitude is entirely determined by the conserved charges of the spacetime, primary hair introduces an additional independent integration constant. This property makes primary-hair solutions especially useful in phenomenological studies, since they allow genuine scalar-field effects in the strong-gravity regime to be separated from those arising solely from changes in mass or gauge charges. This provides a consistent framework for probing deviations from General Relativity within scalar–tensor theories containing a single propagating scalar degree of freedom, including both minimal and non-minimal couplings. Although Horndeski theory was historically regarded as the most general scalar–tensor theory with second-order field equations, later developments have extended this structure to the broader classes of Beyond-Horndeski and Degenerate Higher-Order Scalar-Tensor (DHOST) theories [18–23]. Within this extended landscape, the scalarized black-hole solutions constructed in Ref. [24] are particularly suitable for detailed investigation. These spacetimes are asymptotically flat, admit exact analytic forms, and are characterized by a minimal set of parameters. They arise in shift-symmetric, parity-preserving Beyond-Horndeski/DHOST-type theories and therefore provide a well-controlled setting to study how scalar hair modifies horizon structure, thermodynamic behaviour, photon dynamics, and radiative processes.

Significant progress has recently been made in constructing and analyzing primary-hair black holes in these theories. The foundational solution was presented in Ref. [24], while more general solution-generating methods were developed in Refs. [25, 26]. Thermodynamic aspects were investigated in Ref. [27], and stability and shadow-related phenomenology were discussed in Ref. [28]. Recent progress in perturbation theory for these primary-hair solutions has also been reported in Ref. [29]. These developments are connected to earlier work on no-hair theorems and hairy black-hole solutions in shift-symmetric scalar–tensor theories [30–35].

A second physically motivated ingredient is the presence of a cloud of strings. String-cloud configurations, originally introduced by Letelier [36], represent a continuous distribution of one-dimensional objects and modify the spacetime through a conical-deficit-like contribution. Such a term is analogous in spirit to the deficit generated by a global monopole [37]. It

changes the horizon radius and can affect lensing, accretion, shadows, and particle motion. Black-hole solutions sourced by a cloud of strings have been studied in Einstein gravity and in several modified-gravity settings [38–41]. Combining a primary-hair sector with a string cloud is therefore a natural way to examine the interplay between two different mechanisms that deform the Schwarzschild geometry: one associated with an independent scalar degree of freedom, and the other associated with an extended matter distribution producing a deficit-angle-type modification.

The motivation for the present model is twofold. First, the scalarized core governs the short-distance behavior of the geometry and can modify the horizon structure, temperature, and photon region. Second, the string cloud affects the asymptotic normalization and introduces a matter-induced deformation that can enlarge characteristic radii. Since thermodynamic observables, black-hole shadows, and emission spectra depend simultaneously on near-horizon and photon-sphere properties, the combined system provides a useful setting for identifying which effects are driven mainly by scalar hair and which are driven mainly by the string cloud.

The purpose of the present work is to study this interplay systematically. We begin with the spacetime geometry and the horizon structure, then derive the Hawking temperature, entropy, first law, Smarr relation, heat capacity, and Gibbs free energy. We subsequently analyze the sparsity of Hawking radiation, the photon sphere and black-hole shadow, and the high-energy approximation to the spectral energy emission rate. Throughout the paper, we complement the analytical formulae with numerical plots. These figures are not merely illustrative: they are used to identify physically allowed regions, characterize changes in compactness and stability, and clarify the observable consequences of the parameters α , β , and λ .

II. GEOMETRY AND HORIZON STRUCTURE

The black-hole branch studied here belongs to the shift-symmetric, parity-preserving scalar–tensor sector discussed in Refs. [24, 25]. A compact representation of the underlying theory is provided by the beyond-Horndeski/DHOST-type action

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left[\frac{M_{\text{Pl}}^2}{2} R + K(X) + G_4(X)R + G_{4X}(X) \left((\Box\phi)^2 - \nabla_\mu \nabla_\nu \phi \nabla^\mu \nabla^\nu \phi \right) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{bH}}(X, \phi) \right], \quad (1)$$

where $X \equiv -\frac{1}{2}\nabla_\mu \phi \nabla^\mu \phi$, $G_4(X)$ is the coupling multiplying the Ricci scalar, and $G_{4X} \equiv dG_4/dX$ controls the derivative coupling sector. The theory is invariant under the shift symmetry $\phi \rightarrow \phi + c$.

We first consider a static, spherically symmetric line element

$$ds^2 = -f(r)dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (2)$$

where the scalarized black-hole solution of Ref. [24] is de-

scribed by

$$f(r) = 1 - \frac{2M}{r} + \eta q^4 \left[\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)^2} \right]. \quad (3)$$

Here, M is the asymptotic mass, q is the scalar-hair integration constant, η is a coupling parameter with dimension $(\text{length})^4$, and λ is a length scale controlling the scalarized core with dimension (length) . It is convenient to define

$$\beta = \eta q^4, \quad (4)$$

so that the scalar-hair contribution is governed by the single parameter β . The Schwarzschild solution is recovered for $\beta \rightarrow 0$.

To incorporate a cloud of strings, we consider the Nambu-Goto action [36]

$$S_{\text{CS}} = \int \sqrt{-\gamma} \mathcal{M} d\lambda^0 d\lambda^1 = \int \mathcal{M} \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} \Sigma^{\mu\nu} \Sigma_{\mu\nu}} d\lambda^0 d\lambda^1, \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{M} characterizes the string, (λ^0, λ^1) are worldsheet coordinates [42], and

$$\gamma = \det \left(g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda^a} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \lambda^b} \right), \quad \Sigma_{\mu\nu} = \epsilon^{ab} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda^a} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \lambda^b}. \quad (6)$$

The corresponding energy-momentum tensor has nonzero components

$$T_t^{(CS)} = \rho^{\text{CS}} = \frac{\alpha}{r^2} = T_r^{(CS)}, \quad T_\theta^{(CS)} = T_\varphi^{(CS)} = 0, \quad (7)$$

where α is the string-cloud parameter.

The resulting black hole with primary scalar hair surrounded by a cloud of strings is written as

$$ds^2 = -f(r) dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\varphi^2), \quad (8)$$

with lapse function

$$f(r) = 1 - \alpha - \frac{2M}{r} + \beta \left[\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{r}{\lambda}\right)^2} \right]. \quad (9)$$

In the limit $q \rightarrow 0$, equivalently $\beta \rightarrow 0$, this spacetime reduces to the Letelier black hole [36]. The parameter α shifts the asymptotic value of the lapse function from unity to $1 - \alpha$, while β changes the short-distance behavior through the scalar-hair profile. The length scale λ determines how rapidly this profile decays outside the scalarized core. The behavior of the metric function (9) in the asymptotic limit $r \rightarrow \infty$ is given by

$$f(r) = 1 - \alpha - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{r^2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{r^4}\right), \quad (10)$$

where the charge-like term can be identified as $Q = \sqrt{2\eta} \lambda q^2$, analogous to the electromagnetic charge in the Reissner-Nordström solution of general relativity with a cloud of strings.

In the near-origin limit $r \rightarrow 0$, the metric function takes the form

$$f(r) = 1 - \alpha - \frac{2\tilde{M}}{r} - \Lambda_{\text{eff}} r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4), \quad (11)$$

where

$$2\tilde{M} = 2M - \frac{\pi}{2} \eta \lambda q^4, \quad \Lambda_{\text{eff}} = \frac{2\eta q^4}{3\lambda^2}. \quad (12)$$

Thus, for $\eta < 0$, the effective core is de Sitter-like, whereas for $\eta > 0$ it is Anti-de Sitter (AdS)-like. This small-radius behavior shows explicitly that the scalar sector changes the internal structure of the spacetime, while the string cloud produces an additional deficit-like deformation through the parameter α .

FIG. 1. Metric function $f(r)$ for three one-parameter families. Panel (i) varies the scalar-hair parameter β at fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (ii) varies the string-cloud parameter α at fixed $\beta = 1.0$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (iii) varies the scalar length scale λ at fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 1.0$. The dashed horizontal line marks $f(r) = 0$, whose intersections with the curves determine the horizon positions.

Figure 1 displays the behavior of the lapse function for representative parameter families. In Fig. 1(i), negative values of β lower the metric function in the near-horizon region and move the outer zero of $f(r)$ to larger radii. This corresponds to a less compact configuration. Positive values of β , on the other hand, raise the short-distance part of the lapse function and can generate a richer root structure, including multiple horizons or, for sufficiently large positive β , regions in which the physical black-hole horizon disappears. Thus, the sign and magnitude of β control the departure from the

Schwarzschild-like branch.

Figure 1(ii) isolates the effect of the string cloud. Increasing α lowers the asymptotic value of $f(r)$ and shifts the horizon outward. This is consistent with the interpretation of the string cloud as introducing a conical-deficit contribution that weakens the effective asymptotic normalization and enlarges the black-hole radius. Figure 1(iii) shows that increasing λ changes the spatial extent of the scalar-hair correction. For the parameter choice displayed, larger λ enhances the near-core contribution and shifts the outer zero inward, indicating that the scale of the scalarized core directly affects the compactness of the solution.

The event horizon r_h is defined by the largest positive root of

$$f(r_h) = 0. \quad (13)$$

Using this condition, the mass parameter can be expressed as

$$M = \frac{r_h}{2} \left[1 - \alpha + \beta \left(\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r_h}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2} \right) \right]. \quad (14)$$

This relation will be used below to formulate the thermodynamics in terms of the horizon radius.

Figure 2 quantifies the horizon displacement observed in Fig. 1. The first panel shows that r_h decreases monotonically as β increases. Therefore, within the displayed range, positive scalar hair makes the black hole more compact, whereas negative β increases the horizon radius. This behavior is useful because it provides a direct geometric interpretation of the scalar-hair parameter. The second panel shows a strong monotonic increase of r_h with α , confirming that the string cloud enlarges the horizon. The third panel shows that, for fixed α and β , increasing λ decreases the horizon radius. This indicates that the scalar length scale not only rescales the profile but also shifts the radial location at which the scalar correction competes with the Schwarzschild and string-cloud terms.

III. THERMODYNAMICS

We now derive the Hawking temperature and the associated thermodynamic quantities. For a static and spherically symmetric metric, the surface gravity is

$$\kappa = -\frac{1}{2} \lim_{r \rightarrow r_h} \frac{\partial_r g_{tt}}{\sqrt{-g_{tt}g_{rr}}} = \frac{1}{2} f'(r_h). \quad (15)$$

The Hawking temperature is then [4]

$$T = \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} = \frac{1}{4\pi r_h} \left[1 - \alpha - \frac{2\beta(r_h/\lambda)^2}{(1 + (r_h/\lambda)^2)^2} \right]. \quad (16)$$

For later convenience, we define

$$\Delta_h = 1 - \alpha - \frac{2\beta(r_h/\lambda)^2}{(1 + (r_h/\lambda)^2)^2}, \quad (17)$$

so that $T = \Delta_h/(4\pi r_h)$. The condition $T > 0$ imposes $\Delta_h > 0$ and selects the physical thermodynamic domain.

Figure 3 shows the Hawking temperature as a function of the horizon radius. In all panels, the temperature decreases

FIG. 2. Outer horizon radius r_h as a function of the model parameters. Panel (i) shows $r_h(\beta)$ for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (ii) shows $r_h(\alpha)$ for fixed $\beta = 1.0$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (iii) shows $r_h(\lambda)$ for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 1.0$. Only positive physical horizon radii are displayed.

rapidly as r_h grows, reflecting the familiar inverse-radius behavior of Schwarzschild-like black holes. The scalar-hair and string-cloud parameters modify this decay through the factor Δ_h and through the normalization $(1 - \alpha)^{-1/2}$. In Fig. 3(i), different values of β produce the largest deviations at small and intermediate radii; for large r_h , the curves approach the same qualitative inverse-radius falloff. Figure 3(ii) shows that increasing α changes both the asymptotic normalization and the thermodynamic domain. Figure 3(iii) demonstrates that λ mainly affects the region where r_h is comparable to the scalar length scale, while large black holes are less sensitive to the detailed scalar-hair profile.

FIG. 3. Hawking temperature T as a function of the horizon radius r_h . The panels show the effects of varying β , α , and λ , respectively. Only the positive-temperature branch is physically relevant.

Assuming the Bekenstein–Hawking area law, the entropy is [4, 43]

$$S = \int \frac{dM}{T} = \pi r_h^2. \quad (18)$$

It follows that

$$2TS = \frac{r_h}{2} \left[1 - \alpha - \frac{2\beta(r_h/\lambda)^2}{(1 + (r_h/\lambda)^2)^2} \right]. \quad (19)$$

If the scalar-hair parameter q , coupling constant η and λ are regarded as thermodynamic variables, then $M = M(S, \alpha, \eta, q, \lambda)$ and the modified first law reads [44]

$$dM = T dS + \Psi d\alpha + \Phi dq + \Theta d\eta + \Sigma d\lambda, \quad (20)$$

where the conjugates are

$$\Phi = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial q} \right)_S = 2\eta q^3 r_h \left(\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r_h}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{r_h^2}{\lambda^2}} \right), \quad (21)$$

$$\Psi = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial \alpha} \right)_{S,q} = -\frac{r_h}{2}, \quad (22)$$

$$\Theta = \frac{\partial M}{\partial \eta} = \frac{r_h}{2} q^4 \left(\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r_h}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2} \right), \quad (23)$$

and

$$\Sigma = \frac{\partial M}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{r_h}{2} \beta \times \left[\frac{\lambda^2}{r_h(\lambda^2 + r_h^2)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)}{\lambda} + \frac{2r_h^3}{(\lambda^2 + r_h^2)^2} \right]. \quad (24)$$

With these quantities, the corresponding Smarr-type relation using Euler's theorem may be written as [45]

$$M = 2TS - q\Phi + 4\eta\Theta + \Sigma\lambda \quad (25)$$

which holds in the present case.

The heat capacity at fixed scalar hair is

$$C = \frac{dM}{dT} = T \left(\frac{dS}{dT} \right)_q = 2\pi r_h^2 \times \left[\frac{1 - \alpha - \frac{2\beta\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2\right)^2}}{-\left(1 - \alpha - \frac{2\beta\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2\right)^2}\right) - \frac{4\beta\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2\left(1 - \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2\right)}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)^2\right)^3}} \right]. \quad (26)$$

For $\beta \rightarrow 0$, this expression reduces to the standard negative heat capacity of a Schwarzschild-type black hole with the string-cloud normalization.

Figure 4 displays the heat capacity as a function of the horizon radius. This quantity is the central diagnostic of local thermodynamic stability. In the regions where $C < 0$, the black hole heats up as it loses mass, as in the Schwarzschild case, and the branch is locally unstable in the canonical ensemble. By contrast, regions with $C > 0$ correspond to locally stable configurations. The divergences of C occur when the denominator of Eq. (26) vanishes, namely when $dT/dr_h = 0$. These points separate branches with different stability properties and may be interpreted as phase-transition-like points.

Figure 4(i) shows the effect of varying the scalar-hair parameter β while keeping $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$ fixed. For negative β , the heat capacity is mostly negative over the displayed range, indicating a predominantly Schwarzschild-like unstable behavior. As β increases toward positive values, a positive- C branch develops at smaller and intermediate horizon radii. This indicates that the scalar-hair contribution can create a locally stable thermodynamic sector. The vertical structures and sign changes visible in this panel are associated with the zeros of dT/dr_h , where the heat capacity diverges, and the system changes stability branch.

Figure 4(ii) isolates the effect of the string-cloud parameter α for fixed $\beta = 1.0$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Increasing α shifts the divergence structure and enlarges the region in which positive

FIG. 4. Heat capacity C as a function of the horizon radius. The displayed range is truncated to make the sign changes and divergences visible. Positive values of C correspond to locally stable branches, whereas negative values indicate local thermodynamic instability. Divergences signal possible transitions between thermodynamic branches.

heat capacity appears. This behavior shows that the cloud of strings does not merely rescale the thermodynamic quantities; it also changes the stability domain by modifying the effective horizon structure and the temperature gradient. For sufficiently large α , the positive- C branch becomes more pronounced, while the negative- C branch is pushed toward larger values of r_h .

Figure 4(iii) displays the dependence on the scalar length scale λ for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 1.0$. In this case, the heat capacity remains mostly negative throughout the plotted range. Increasing λ shifts the curves and changes the radial interval

over which the scalar-hair correction is relevant, but it does not generate a large positive- C sector for the representative parameters chosen here. Thus, while β and α can produce sizable locally stable branches, the variation of λ in panel (iii) mainly deforms the Schwarzschild-like unstable branch rather than qualitatively changing its thermodynamic character.

Finally, the Gibbs free energy is obtained as

$$G = M - TS = \frac{r_h}{4} \left[1 - \alpha + 2\beta \left\{ \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_h}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r_h}{\lambda}} + \frac{1 + 2(r_h/\lambda)^2}{(1 + (r_h/\lambda)^2)^2} \right\} \right]. \quad (27)$$

This quantity complements the local stability analysis based on the heat capacity. While the sign of C characterizes local thermodynamic stability, the sign and branch structure of G provide information about global thermodynamic preference in the canonical ensemble. In particular, branches with lower Gibbs free energy are thermodynamically favored, and crossings of the line $G = 0$ may indicate changes in the global thermodynamic behavior.

Figure 5 displays the Gibbs free energy as a function of the Hawking temperature. The curves are parametrized by the horizon radius r_h , and only the physical branches with $T > 0$ are shown. The dashed horizontal line marks $G = 0$. Configurations above this line have positive Gibbs free energy, whereas configurations below it have negative Gibbs free energy. Therefore, negative- G branches are globally preferred relative to the reference background, while positive- G branches are thermodynamically less favorable.

Figure 5(i) shows the effect of the scalar-hair parameter β for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. The scalar-hair contribution strongly affects both the magnitude and the sign of the Gibbs free energy. For negative values of β , part of the branch extends below $G = 0$, indicating the existence of globally favored configurations in the corresponding temperature interval. As β increases toward positive values, the curves are shifted upward and become predominantly positive. Thus, in the representative parameter range considered here, negative scalar-hair corrections favor the appearance of negative- G sectors, whereas positive scalar-hair corrections tend to suppress them. This behavior is consistent with the role of β in modifying the horizon structure and the temperature profile.

Figure 5(ii) isolates the influence of the string-cloud parameter α while keeping $\beta = 1.0$ and $\lambda = 1.0$ fixed. The curves exhibit a cusp-like structure in the G - T plane, indicating the presence of multiple thermodynamic branches at nearby temperatures. Increasing α changes both the location and the height of these branches. In the displayed range, the Gibbs free energy remains mostly positive, showing that these configurations are globally disfavored relative to the chosen reference background. Nevertheless, the deformation of the cusp with increasing α demonstrates that the cloud of strings significantly reshapes the global thermodynamic landscape. This provides a global counterpart to the local stability changes identified by heat capacity measurements.

Figure 5(iii) displays the dependence on the scalar length scale λ for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 1.0$. In this case, the Gibbs free energy remains positive over most of the plotted domain. Varying λ mainly shifts the branches in the G - T plane and

FIG. 5. Gibbs free energy G as a function of the Hawking temperature T . Panel (i) shows the effect of varying the scalar-hair parameter β for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (ii) shows the effect of varying the string-cloud parameter α for fixed $\beta = 1.0$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (iii) shows the effect of varying the scalar length scale λ for fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 1.0$. The dashed horizontal line corresponds to $G = 0$ and separates branches with positive and negative Gibbs free energy.

changes their curvature, without generating a large negative- G region for the representative parameters chosen here. This shows that λ , which controls the radial extension of the scalar-hair correction, mostly deforms the thermodynamic branches rather than inducing a qualitative change in the preferred phase.

Overall, Fig. 5 shows that the scalar-hair parameter β plays the dominant role in determining whether negative Gibbs free energy branches appear. The string-cloud parameter α and the scalar scale λ primarily reshape the branch structure and shift the location of the curves. Together with the heat-capacity behavior shown in Fig. 4, the Gibbs-free-energy analysis indicates that the black hole may exhibit locally sta-

ble and globally preferred sectors depending on the interplay between scalar hair and the surrounding cloud of strings.

IV. SPARSITY OF RADIATION

Hawking radiation is often described as approximately thermal radiation emitted with a temperature proportional to the surface gravity [4]. However, for an asymptotic observer, the spectrum is not exactly Planckian because the curved spacetime outside the horizon acts as a frequency-dependent filter. This effect is encoded in greybody factors [46, 47]. Another important feature is the sparsity of the radiation: the average time between successive emitted quanta is much larger than the characteristic time scale associated with each quantum [48–55].

Following the standard definition, the sparsity parameter is

$$\psi = \frac{C_s}{\bar{g}} \frac{\lambda_t^2}{A_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (28)$$

where

$$\lambda_t = 2\pi T^{-1}, \quad A_{\text{eff}} = \frac{27}{4} A_{\text{BH}}(r_h) \quad (29)$$

where $A_{\text{BH}} = 4\pi r_h^2$ is the horizon area.

For the normalization used here, this gives

$$\psi = \frac{64\pi^3}{27} \frac{1}{\Delta_h^2}, \quad (30)$$

where Δ_h is defined in Eq. (17).

Figure 6 shows the sparsity parameter. The logarithmic scale is essential because the radiation is extremely dilute, with ψ remaining much larger than unity over the plotted domain. In Fig. 6(i), varying β produces sharp enhancements when Δ_h becomes small. Since $\psi \propto \Delta_h^{-2}$, configurations close to low-temperature or near-extremal behavior lead to very large sparsity. Figure 6(ii) shows that increasing α tends to raise the sparsity, consistent with Eq. (30). Figure 6(iii) indicates that the scalar length scale can generate a broad maximum: the radiation becomes most sparse when the scalar correction significantly suppresses the effective temperature, and then approaches a more slowly varying regime at larger radii. Overall, the figure confirms that the radiation is far from a continuous classical flux.

V. PHOTON SPHERE AND SHADOW

The photon sphere is determined by unstable circular null geodesics [56, 57]. For the metric in Eq. (8), the first-order equations of motion for null geodesics may be written as

$$\frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{E}{f(r)}, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{d\varphi}{d\tau} = \frac{L}{r^2}, \quad (32)$$

$$\left(\frac{dr}{d\tau}\right)^2 = V_{\text{eff}}, \quad (33)$$

FIG. 6. Sparsity parameter ψ as a function of r_h . A logarithmic vertical scale is used because ψ spans several orders of magnitude. The large values $\psi \gg 1$ demonstrate that the Hawking flux remains highly sparse throughout the physical domain.

where τ is an affine parameter and

$$V_{\text{eff}} = E^2 - \frac{L^2}{r^2} f(r). \quad (34)$$

Here, E is the conserved energy and L is the conserved angular momentum of particles. This effective potential governs the photon dynamics around the black hole.

The circular null orbit conditions $V_{\text{eff}} = 0$ and $\partial_r V_{\text{eff}} = 0$ imply the following relation:

$$f(r_s) - \frac{r_s}{2} f'(r_s) = 0, \quad (35)$$

which determines the photon-sphere radius r_s . An exact analytical solution of Eq. (35) is difficult to obtain in closed form. We therefore determine the photon-sphere radius numerically for representative values of the geometric parameters η , q , λ , and α .

$\eta q^4 (\downarrow) \backslash \alpha (\rightarrow)$	0.0	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
0.0	3.0000	3.1579	3.3333	3.5294	3.7500
0.1	2.9999	3.1578	3.3332	3.5293	3.7499
0.2	2.9981	3.1560	3.3314	3.5274	3.7480
0.3	2.9902	3.1480	3.3234	3.5194	3.7399
0.4	2.9690	3.1266	3.3017	3.4975	3.7179
0.5	2.9233	3.0805	3.2552	3.4507	3.6707

TABLE I. Numerical values of the photon sphere r_s/M for varying ηq^4 and α . Here $\lambda/M = 1$.

For a static observer at radius r_0 , the shadow radius is [58]

$$R_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{f(r_0)}{f(r_s)}}. \quad (36)$$

The numerical results for the photon sphere and shadow radii are presented in Tables I–II, showing their dependence on the parameters ηq^4 and the cloud of strings parameter α , while the coupling constant λ is kept fixed.

For an observer at infinity, where $f(r_0) \rightarrow 1 - \alpha$, this becomes

$$R_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{1 - \alpha}{1 - \alpha - \frac{2M}{r_s} + \beta \left[\frac{\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{r_s}{\lambda}\right)}{\frac{r_s}{\lambda}} + \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{r_s}{\lambda}\right)^2} \right]}}. \quad (37)$$

The photon sphere and the shadow are central observational quantities because they control the high-frequency capture cross section and encode strong-field deviations from Schwarzschild geometry [56, 57, 59, 60].

Tables I and II, together with Fig. 7, show the photon-sphere and shadow radii. The tables provide representative numerical values for fixed $\lambda/M = 1$, confirming that the photon-sphere radius and the shadow radius increase with the string-cloud parameter α and decrease as the scalar-hair combination ηq^4 is increased. The continuous plots in Fig. 7 extend this comparison to wider parameter intervals and include the dependence on λ .

In all panels of Fig. 7, R_{sh} is larger than r_s , as expected for a distant observer, because the observed angular size is controlled by the critical impact parameter rather than by the coordinate radius of the photon orbit itself. Figure 7(i) shows

$\eta q^4 (\downarrow) \backslash \alpha (\rightarrow)$	0.0	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
0.0	4.6476	4.8599	5.0918	5.3458	5.6250
0.1	4.6474	4.8598	5.0916	5.3456	5.6249
0.2	4.6454	4.8577	5.0896	5.3436	5.6229
0.3	4.6363	4.8487	5.0806	5.3348	5.6141
0.4	4.6118	4.8243	5.0564	5.3107	5.5904
0.5	4.5590	4.7718	5.0043	5.2592	5.5396

TABLE II. Numerical values of the shadow radius R_{sh}/M for varying ηq^4 and α . Here $\lambda/M = 1$, $r_0/M = 10$.

FIG. 7. Photon-sphere radius r_s and shadow radius R_{sh} as functions of β , α , and λ . Only physical solutions with $r_s > r_h$ and $R_{\text{sh}} > 0$ are displayed.

that both r_s and R_{sh} decrease as β increases. This is consistent with the horizon behavior: positive scalar hair makes the compact object appear smaller within the displayed range and reduces the photon-capture region. Figure 7(ii) shows that increasing the string-cloud parameter increases both r_s and R_{sh} ; the cloud of strings therefore produces a larger apparent shadow. Figure 7(iii) indicates that increasing λ decreases the characteristic optical radii for the chosen parameter values, showing that the radial extension of the scalarized core can leave a measurable imprint on the photon region. These results suggest that shadow observations can, in principle, constrain combinations of α , β , and λ .

VI. ENERGY EMISSION RATE

The Hawking emission process may be approximated in the high-energy regime by using the limiting absorption cross section. In this limit, the absorption cross section oscillates around a constant value that can be estimated from the black-hole shadow [61–63]:

$$\sigma_{\text{lim}} \approx \pi R_{\text{sh}}^2. \quad (38)$$

The spectral energy emission rate is then

$$\frac{d^2\mathbb{E}}{d\omega dt} = \frac{2\pi^2 \sigma_{\text{lim}} \omega^3}{e^{\omega/T} - 1} = \frac{2\pi^3 R_{\text{sh}}^2 \omega^3}{e^{\omega/T} - 1}. \quad (39)$$

Using Eq. (16), the exponent may equivalently be written as

$$\frac{\omega}{T} = \frac{4\pi r_h}{\Delta_h} \omega. \quad (40)$$

This form makes it clear that both the shadow radius and the Hawking temperature control the spectrum: R_{sh} fixes the overall effective emitting area, while T fixes the peak position and the exponential decay at high frequencies.

Figure 8 displays the spectral energy emission rate. The curves show the expected Hawking-like behavior: the emission starts from zero at low frequency, increases to a maximum, and then decays due to the Planck factor. Figure 8(i) shows that varying β changes both the height and the location of the spectral peak. This is the combined result of two effects: β modifies the temperature through Δ_h and changes the shadow radius through the photon-sphere equation. Figure 8(ii) demonstrates that increasing α suppresses the emission amplitude and shifts the peak toward smaller frequencies. Physically, this is associated with the enlargement of the horizon and the shadow, together with a reduction in the effective temperature. Figure 8(iii) shows that increasing λ can enhance the emission and shift the peak, because the scalarized core becomes more extended and changes both T and R_{sh} . Thus, the emission rate is a sensitive probe of the combined thermal and optical properties of the spacetime.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated a black hole with primary scalar hair surrounded by a cloud of strings. The spacetime is governed by the string-cloud parameter α , the scalar-hair parameter $\beta = \eta q^4$, and the scalar length scale λ . The metric analysis shows that these parameters have distinct geometric effects. Increasing α enlarges the horizon, while increasing β in the displayed physical range tends to reduce the characteristic radii and makes the configuration more compact. The parameter λ controls the radial extension of the scalar-hair correction and strongly affects the near-core region.

The thermodynamic analysis revealed that the Hawking temperature retains an inverse-radius character but is modified by the factor Δ_h and by the string-cloud contribution. The heat capacity exhibits both positive and negative branches. Negative heat capacity indicates local instability, whereas positive heat capacity indicates local stability. Divergences of the heat capacity mark changes between

FIG. 8. Spectral energy emission rate $d^2\mathbb{E}/d\omega dt$ as a function of the emitted frequency ω . Panel (i) varies β at fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (ii) varies α at fixed $\beta = 0.3$ and $\lambda = 1.0$. Panel (iii) varies λ at fixed $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\beta = 0.3$. The plotted branches satisfy the physical conditions $r_h > 0$, $T > 0$, $r_s > r_h$, and $R_{sh} > 0$.

thermodynamic branches and may be interpreted as phase-transition-like behavior. The Gibbs free energy further shows that local stability and global thermodynamic preference need not coincide: the scalar-hair parameter can generate negative- G branches, while the string-cloud parameter and the scalar length scale mainly reshape the global branch structure.

The sparsity parameter remains well above unity throughout the physical domain, indicating that Hawking radiation is highly sparse rather than continuous. The scalar hair can enhance sparsity when it suppresses the effective temperature, and the string cloud increases the sparsity already in the scalar-hair-free limit. The photon-sphere and shadow analysis showed that the shadow radius is sensitive to all three parameters. In particular, the string cloud increases the apparent shadow size, while positive scalar hair and larger λ reduce it for the representative parameter choices considered here.

Finally, we analyzed the energy emission rate in the high-energy approximation using the shadow radius to estimate the limiting absorption cross section. The resulting spectra have the expected thermal shape, with a peak followed by exponential suppression at high frequency. The peak position and amplitude depend on both the Hawking temperature and the shadow radius, making the emission rate a combined probe of the thermodynamic and optical sectors. These results indicate that black holes with primary scalar hair and cloud-of-strings backgrounds can exhibit rich phenomenology and may provide useful targets for future studies of stability, greybody factors, quasinormal modes, and observational constraints from black-hole shadows.

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